

Preparation of Some Optically Active 2-Methyl Butyl Ethers of Phenols

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Several optically active 2-methyl butyl ethers of phenols have been prepared and the effect of differently substituted groups in the phenolic portion of the ethers on the optical rotation has been studied. The optical rotations in substituted mono-ethers are $p > m > o$. In the case of substituted di-ethers, the optical rotations are $o > p > m$.

In the literature some optically active 2-methyl butyl ethers of phenols have been reported by Welt¹. It was therefore thought of interest to prepare some more optically active 2-methyl butyl ethers of phenols and to study the effect of differently substituted groups in the phenolic portion of the ethers on the optical rotations.

This type of ethers (mono-, di-, or tri-) may be readily obtained through the reaction of alkali phenolates with alkyl halides², which is the basis of Williamson's reaction³. The mechanism possibly is:

The reaction being a bimolecular one, the optical activity is retained when R' contains an asymmetrical carbon atom in the 2-methylbutyl radical, as in our case.

Here in the preparation of optically active 2-methyl butyl ethers of phenols, the differently substituted phenols have been taken and their sodium salt derivatives allowed to react with (+)-1-bromo-2-methylbutane in absolute ethanol. Optically active 2-methylbutyl ethers, prepared from phenols, are listed in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	(+)-2-Methyl butyl ethers.	R.	Formula.	d_{35}^20 .	n_D^{25} .	Found.	Reqd.	$[\alpha]_D^{25}$.
1.	-phenyl	Phenol	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ O	0.9130	1.487	C: 80.10% H: 9.40	80.90% 9.70	+1.635
2.	- <i>m</i> -tolyl	<i>m</i> -Cresol	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ O	1.0577	1.486	C: 80.34 H: 9.68	80.89 10.10	+2.120
3.	- <i>p</i> -tolyl	<i>p</i> -Cresol	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ O	1.0633	1.487	C: 80.32 H: 9.64	80.89 10.10	+2.280
4.	- <i>o</i> -chlorophenyl	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenol	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ OCl	1.0364	1.503	Cl: 17.34	17.88	+1.095
5.	- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Chloro "	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ OCl	1.0371	1.503	Cl: 17.42	17.88	+2.247
6 ^a .	-2,4-dichlorophenyl	2,4-Dichloro "	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ OCl ₂	1.3406	1.517	Cl: 29.78	30.13	+2.064

1. *Ann. chim. phys.* 1895, vii, 6, 137, 138, 139, 140, 141.

2. Vincent, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1883 ii, 40, 106.

3. Williamson, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1852 4, 229.

TABLE I (contd.)

No.	(+)-2-Methyl butyl ethers.	R.	Formula.	d_{25}^20 .	n_D^{34} .	Found.	Reqd. $[\alpha]_D^{34}$.
7.	-2,6-dimethylphenyl	2,6-Dimethyl-phenol	$C_{13}H_{20}O$	1.0800	1.485	C : 79.94% H : 10.1	81.25% +0.6878 10.4
8.	-o-methoxyphenyl	Guaiacol	$C_{12}H_{18}O_2$	1.1479	1.497	C : 74.10 H : 8.93	74.3 +0.9291 9.28
9.	-o-nitrophenyl	o-Nitrophenol	$C_{11}H_{13}O_3N$	1.0741	1.515	N : 0.24	6.70 +0.3386
10.	-m-nitrophenyl	m-Nitro- "	$C_{11}H_{13}O_3N$	1.2655	1.516	N : 6.22	" +1.8050
11.	-p-nitrophenyl	p-Nitro- "	$C_{11}H_{13}O_3N$	1.2730	1.537	N : 6.20	" +2.3270
12.	-1-(2-methoxy-4-carbonyl phenyl)-	Vanillin- "	$C_{13}H_{16}O_3$	1.2338	1.538	C : 69.86 H : 7.80	70.20 8.10 +2.2260
13.	- α -naphthyl	α -Naphthol	$C_{15}H_{18}O$	1.1685	1.563	C : 83.70 H : 8.10	84.10 8.40 +2.2260
14.	- β -naphthyl	β -Naphthol	$C_{15}H_{18}O$	1.1718	1.565	C : 83.70 H : 8.10	84.10 +1.9940 8.40
15.	-1,2-phenylene-di-	Catechol	$C_{16}H_{26}O_2$	1.1187	1.491	C : 76.26 H : 10.20	70.80 +2.6740 10.40
16.	-1,3-phenylene-di-	Resorcinol	$C_{16}H_{26}O_2$	1.1276	1.498	C : 76.46 H : 10.20	76.80 +3.9270 10.40
17.	-1,4-phenylene-di-	Hydroquinone	$C_{16}H_{26}O_2$	0.9675	1.501	C : 76.20 H : 10.10	76.80 +3.3450 10.40
18.	-1,2,3-tri-(+)- β -methyl butyl phenyl tri-	Pyrogallol	$C_{21}H_{36}O_3$	0.9761	1.491	C : 74.80 H : 10.40	75.80 +2.235 10.70
19.	-o-acetoxyphenyl	Methyl salicylate	$C_{13}H_{18}O_3$	1.2035	1.497	C : 69.86 H : 7.90	70.20 +0.7602 8.10
20.	-o-phenoxyphenyl	Salol	$C_{18}H_{20}O_3$	1.1727	1.493	C : 75.84 H : 6.92	76.07 +0.8351 7.04
21.	-o-(methylphenyl carbinone)	o-Hydroxy-acetophenone	$C_{13}H_{16}O_2$	1.1639	1.508	C : 75.30 H : 8.42	75.70 +1.5650 8.70
22.	-o-(diphenyl)-	o-Hydroxy-diphenyl	$C_{17}H_{20}O$	1.1695	1.555	C : 84.90 H : 8.10	85.00 +0.5682 8.30

From Table I, it appears that out of the *ortho*, *para*, and *meta* substituents in the phenolic portion of the ethers, the *para* substituents show higher optical rotation than the *ortho* and the *meta* substituents; also the *meta* substituents show higher rotation than the *ortho* substituents in case of mono-ethers.

In the case of di-ethers, the *ortho*-substituted ether shows the least rotation and *meta* compound shows the highest optical rotation, whereas the *para* compound is in between the two as far as optical rotations are concerned. Further, with the increase of the molecular weight in the phenolic portion of the ether by $-\text{COMe}$, Ph , $-\text{CO}_2\text{Me}$, and CO_2Ph groups, the optical rotation decreased.

EXPERIMENTAL

(-)-2-Methylbutan-1-ol.—Amyl alcohol (from fusel oil) containing 18-20 % of the optically active (-)-2methylbutan-1-ol was fractionally distilled, using a column of 16"

long and the distillate of boiling range 127-28.5° collected; d^{25}_D 0.8279; n_D^{25} 1.407, $[\alpha]^{25}_D$ -4.69° ($l = 1$).

(+)-1-Bromo-2-methylbutane was prepared by treating (-)-2-methylbutan-1-ol (320 g.) with red phosphorus (20.71 g.) and bromine (266.6 g.); yield 48%; n_D^{25} 1.442; d^{25}_D 1.3904; $[\alpha]^{25}_D$ +1.074° ($l = 1$).

General Method of Preparation of Optically Active Ethers.

(a) *Mono-ether.*—Monohydric phenol (0.1M), simple or substituted, and (+)-1-bromo-2-methylbutane (0.1M) were added slowly to sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (0.1M) and absolute ethanol (30 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 5-6 hr., and excess of ethanol and (+)-1-bromo-2-methyl butane were distilled; the residue on decomposition, extraction with ether, purification, evaporation, and distillation under vacuum provided optically active 2-methyl butyl ethers of phenols (Table I).

(b). *Di-ethers.*—To sodium (0.2M), dissolved in absolute ethanol (60 ml), were added dihydric phenol (0.1M) and (+)-1-bromo-2-methylbutane (0.2 M) and the mixture was worked up, as above.

(c). *Tri-ethers.*—To sodium (0.3M), dissolved in absolute ethanol (90 ml), were added trihydric phenol (0.1M) and (+)-1-bromo-2-methylbutane (0.3M); the mixture was further worked up, as above.

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